

Informed Health Choices project

Information for parents and guardians of Year 7 students at Oslo International School (OIS)

October 2016

Dear parent or guardian,

This semester, in science lessons, your child and their classmates will be using learning resources developed as part of the *Informed Health Choices* project. We, researchers working on the project, would like to photograph and video those lessons. This letter explains why. A one-page summary of the project and an opt-out form are attached.

About the project

Our goal is to help people make well-informed health choices. To achieve our goal, we are developing and evaluating learning resources that show people how to make well-informed health choices. These include resources for school children, which we spent about two years developing. There is more information about the project in the attached summary and on our website: www.informedhealthchoices.org.

About testing at OIS last school year

We tested an earlier version of the school resources with Year 7 students at OIS to find out how we could improve them. We watched lessons in which the resources were used, interviewed the teachers and some children individually about their experiences of the resources, and discussed the resources with each class as a group. All of the children in Year 7 participated. The participating science teachers, Pamela Juva and Martin Von Bargen, with Peter McGhan, the science team leader, decided to use the final version of the resources with the new Year 7 students, this semester.

About recording lessons at OIS this semester

While we have not planned to do further testing of the resources at OIS, we do plan on photographing and videoing one or more of the lessons. We will use the photos and videos for non-profit promotional and educational purposes. We are promoting the project so more people use the resources, and to get support to develop and evaluate new resources. We may use photos and video on our website, in presentations, in learning resources or in the media. All of our resources are available for free from our website. Educational purposes are training teachers in using the resources, and training researchers in the methods that we use.

If you do NOT want us to use photos or video in which your child can be identified, please let me know by filling in and returning the opt-out form to your child's science teacher. If, after we have recorded the lessons, you decide that you do not want us to use any photos or video of your child, please let us know as soon as possible, so we can remove any photos or video that we have used in which your child is identifiable. Feel free to contact me with any questions about anything in this letter. Thank you for your time and consideration. We hope your child enjoys and learns from using the resources.

Best regards,

Dr. Andy Oxman, on behalf of the Informed Health Choices team
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Informed Health Choices

Who is behind the Informed Health Choices project?

Our team has experience in health research, design and education. The main partner organisations are the Norwegian Institute of Public Health and the College of Health Sciences at Makerere University in Kamapala, Uganda.

What problem does the project address?

We face endless claims about how to care for our health. Many of these claims are unreliable. When people act on unreliable claims about health or fail to act on reliable ones—in other words, when people make uninformed health choices—they may waste time and money, and suffer unnecessarily.

How does the project address the problem?

We are systematically developing and evaluating learning resources to help people understand the differences between reliable and unreliable claims about health, and how to use reliable evidence to make well-informed choices—in other words, how to think critically about health. For school children, we have developed a textbook called *The Health Choices Book*, which is centred on a comic story. The book and all of our other resources are available for free on our website.

Why focus on children?

Children should not make important choices about their health on their own. However, it is important to prepare them for the choices that they will make as teenagers and adults.

Where can I find more information?

www.informedhealthchoices.org

Informed Health Choices project

Opt-out form

Oslo International School

Please fill in and return this form if you do not want us to use photos or video in which your child is identifiable.

Note that any photos and video will only be used for non-profit promotional and educational purposes.

Name of parent or guardian:

Name of child:

I do not wish for my child to be identifiable in:

- Photos
- Video

I do not wish for photos or video in which my child is identifiable to be used:

- On the *Informed Health Choices* website
- In presentations about *Informed Health Choices*
- In *Informed Health Choices* learning resources
- In media coverage of *Informed Health Choices*

Date:

Signature:

**DECLARATION OF CONSENT TO USE OF RECORDINGS
FOR NON-PROFIT, EDUCATIONAL USE**

I agree to the use of quotes, pictures or video of me collected as part of the Informed Healthcare Choices project to be used for nonprofit, educational purposes in versions of the resources that they are developing and presentations about the project. I understand that I can ask for any quote, picture or video of me to be removed from materials or presentations at any time.

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Telephone number:

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Pupil: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Guardian: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Witness: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____